

ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS OF DRINKING WATER QUALITY AND ITS IMPACT ON PUBLIC HEALTH IN INDIA: BIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS

Shilpi Rai

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics
Government P. G. College Hamirpur, Uttar Pradesh, India
E-mail: raishilpi06@gmail.com

Abstract

Viksit Bharat @ 2047 aims to make India a developed nation, with secure, high-quality and sustainable drinking water access as a core pillar. Countries throughout the world are concerned with the effects of unclean drinking water because water-borne diseases are a major cause of morbidity and mortality. Clean drinking water is important for overall health and plays a substantial role in infant and child health and survival. The World Health Organization estimated that globally, about 1.8 million people die from diarrheal diseases annually, many of which have been linked to diseases acquired from the consumption of contaminated waters and seafood. Human is considered as a resource and capital for an economy. Therefore human resources are the major assets or wealth of the economy and their health play a vital role in increasing the efficiency of these human resources development. Today most of the ground water and surface water resources become polluted. In this research paper, quality of drinking water has been analyzed on the bases of its effects upon human health. Poor quality of drinking water leads to poor human health and increase in water borne diseases cases or deaths (Diarrhoea, Typhoid, Malaria and Cholera).

Key Words: Quality of Drinking Water, Water Borne Diseases, Public Health

Introduction

Viksit Bharat @ 2047 aims to make India a developed nation, with secure, high-quality and sustainable drinking water access as a core pillar. Countries throughout the world are concerned with the effects of unclean drinking water because water-borne diseases are a major cause of morbidity and mortality. Clean drinking water is important for overall health and plays a substantial role in infant and child health and survival. The World Health Organization estimated that globally, about 1.8 million people die from diarrheal diseases annually, many of which have been linked to diseases acquired from the consumption of contaminated waters and seafood. Human is considered as a resource and capital for an economy. Therefore human resources are the major assets or wealth of the economy and their health play a vital role in increasing the efficiency of these human resources development.

On the other side, human body consists of 70% water and water is also a primary requirement for human being after air for breathing, same as everyone have needs to drink water for living. No one can live without water, so water (surface or ground water) is a part of hydrosphere of environment. Today most of the ground water and surface

water resources become polluted. Sometimes, water can be polluted due to the mismanagement of water, imperfect storage management and low facility or low awareness of hygiene and sanitation. Diseases easily transfer into human body due to polluted water either by drinking or sewage water. These diseases are very harmful for the human body. They are called water borne disease in which major diseases are Diarrhoea, Typhoid, Malaria and Cholera. Water related diseases are the most common cause of deaths.

In this research paper, quality of drinking water has been analyzed on the bases of its effects upon human health. Bad quality of drinking water leads to poor human health and increase in water borne diseases cases or deaths (Diarrhoea, Typhoid, Malaria and Cholera).

Objectives

Based on the above background of quality of drinking water, the paper studies the following aspects:

1. To analyze the status of drinking water quality in India
2. To highlight the status water borne diseases in India.

Data Sources & Methodology

The study is based on the analysis of secondary data. The data from surveys conducted by The Human Development Report, World Health Organization Report and Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India are used for analysis. Methodology of computing the Case Fatality Rate (CFR) in selected indicators, India

Indicator	Source	CFR
Water borne diseases (Diarrhoea, Typhoid, Malaria and Cholera).	Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India	CFR=(death cases/ morbidity) *100

Water Borne Diseases in India

Table-1 shows that availability of total drinking water in the percentage of population and number of water borne diseases cases (Diarrhoea, Typhoid, Malaria and Cholera). Morbidity due to diarrhoea has been reached at 1.3 crore in 2024 while it was 88 lakh in 2005. Its highest over the two decades was 1.39 crore in 2021 while its lowest value was 77.0 lakh in 2007. Average of Morbidity due to Diarrhea is approximately 1.07 crore in two decades. Morbidity due to typhoid, malaria and cholera has been 20 lakh, 7.6 lakh and 1251 respectively in 2024 while it was 4.5 lakh, 20 lakh and 3807 respectively in 2005. Average morbidity due to these diseases are 11.7 lakh, 14.4 lakh and 2645 respectively within two decades. The highest value of morbidity due to typhoid is 22 lakh in 2022, morbidity due to malaria is 20.8 lakh in 2006 and morbidity due to cholera is 5155 in 2015. The lowest value of morbidity due to typhoid is 4.5 lakh in 2005, morbidity due to malaria is 7.6 lakh in 2024 and morbidity due to cholera is 494 in 2022. (Table.1)

Table-1: Morbidity Due to Water Borne Diseases at National Level

Year	Availability of Total Drinking Water (in the percentage of population)	Morbidity Due to Diarrhoea	Morbidity Due to Typhoid	Morbidity Due to Malaria	Morbidity Due to Cholera
2005	79.02	8812925	452378	2031790	3807
2006	79.54	8171206	490195	2085484	4178
2007	80.36	7703029	488033	2010790	3455
2008	81.18	10510476	596684	1869403	2893
2009	82.01	10487238	658301	1915363	4695
2010	82.84	10978459	694291	1816342	3156
2011	83.86	8291807	789004	1785129	1939
2012	84.75	9478813	694862	1508927	2635

2013	85.30	11408666	916161	1526210	2680
2014	86.12	8215296	1039311	1563574	3482
2015	86.94	10112845	1034642	1599986	5155
2016	87.76	10231049	1062446	1310656	2341
2017	88.59	11701755	1477699	1067824	1583
2018	89.41	11413610	1650145	881730	1642
2019	90.22	11748631	1736687	1102205	969
2020	91.04	12233379	1937413	1169261	3102
2021	91.86	13923275	1518859	1087285	2045
2022	92.68	12927212	2215805	844558	494
2023	93.48	12920180	199944	943961	1398
2024	94.30	13178739	2096154	765180	1251
Average	86.56	10722429	1177425	1445333	2645
S.D.	4.82	1849674	595450	439819	1258
COV	23.21	17.25	50.57	30.43	47.60

Sources: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India (Various Session), Red Value=Projected Values

Table-1 shows that all four series of morbidity due to water borne diseases has so much variation (COV) in overall. The highest variation is found in typhoid cases then after in cholera cases. Very low variation (COV) is found in diarrhoea cases. Drinking water availability also has variation of 23.21%. The result shows that the number of people suffering from diarrhoea is the highest among the four major water borne diseases. After year 2005, it has been seen that the number of people suffering from diarrhoea and typhoid has increased with the increasing availability of drinking water but malaria and cholera has decreased with the increasing availability of drinking water.

Table-2 shows that availability of total drinking water in the percentage of population and number of water borne diseases cases (Diarrhoea, Typhoid, Malaria and Cholera). Number of death cases from diarrhoea has been reached to 968 in 2024 while it was 2901 in 2005. Its highest over the two decades was 4709 in 2008 while its lowest value was 968 in 2024. Average of the diarrhoea death cases is 2126 in two decades. Number of typhoid, malaria and cholera death cases has been found 322, 268 and 03 respectively in 2024 while it was 396, 1033 and 18 respectively in 2005. Average death cases of these diseases are 486, 789 and 06 respectively within two decades. The highest value of typhoid death cases is 839 in 2008, malaria death cases is 1707 in 2011 and cholera death cases is 18 in 2005. The lowest value of typhoid death cases is 279 in 2021, malaria death cases is 167 in 2023 and cholera death cases is 01 in

2013 & 2017. (Table-2)

Table-2: Water Born Diseases Death Cases at National Level

Year	Availability of Total Drinking Water (in the percentage of population)	Number of Diarrhoea Deaths	Number of Typhoid Deaths	Number of Malaria Deaths	Number of Cholera Deaths
2005	79.02	2901	396	1033	18
2006	79.54	2273	606	1005	6
2007	80.36	2670	581	1002	10
2008	81.18	4709	839	977	2
2009	82.01	2939	805	949	7
2010	82.84	2147	786	963	6
2011	83.86	2669	658	1707	3
2012	84.75	2328	393	1311	3
2013	85.30	2865	338	1055	1
2014	86.12	3594	421	1144	12
2015	86.94	1388	379	1023	9
2016	87.76	1269	346	754	10
2017	88.59	1647	428	519	1
2018	89.41	1629	387	440	9
2019	90.22	1337	429	562	5
2020	91.04	1216	468	384	3
2021	91.86	1540	279	331	4
2022	92.68	1331	511	194	3
2023	93.48	1090	339	167	3
2024	94.30	968	322	268	3
Average	86.56	2126	486	789	6
S.D.	4.82	970	170	413	4
COV	23.21	45.65	35.11	52.33	72.95

Sources: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India, Red Value=Projected Values

Table-2 shows that all four death series of water borne diseases has so much variation (COV) in overall. The highest variation is found in cholera cases then after in malaria cases. Very low variation (COV) is found in typhoid cases. Availability of drinking water also has variation of 23.21% that is the lowest in all series. Death from all water borne diseases has decreased with the increasing availability of total drinking water that is measured in the percentage of population since 2005. But death due to diarrhoea is highest among all water borne diseases. Resultant, it can be said that the main cause of death of people is diarrhoea among four major water borne diseases with in India.

Table-3 depicts that Case Fatality Rate of water borne diseases. Case Fatality rates of diarrhoea, typhoid, malaria

and cholera are 0.01, 0.02, 0.04 and 0.24 respectively in 2023 while these are 0.03, 0.09, 0.05 and 0.47 respectively in 2004.

Average of case fatality rate is highest in cholera disease then after in typhoid and lowest in diarrhoea disease. Highest variation is found in typhoid disease then after in cholera disease and lowest in malaria disease.

Table-3: Case Fatality Rate of Water Born Diseases at National Level

Year	Case Fatality Rate of Diarrhoea	Case Fatality Rate of Typhoid	Case Fatality Rate of Malaria	Case Fatality Rate of Cholera
2005	0.03	0.09	0.05	0.47
2006	0.03	0.12	0.05	0.14
2007	0.03	0.12	0.05	0.29
2008	0.04	0.14	0.05	0.07
2009	0.03	0.12	0.05	0.15
2010	0.02	0.11	0.05	0.19
2011	0.03	0.08	0.10	0.15
2012	0.02	0.06	0.09	0.11
2013	0.03	0.04	0.07	0.04
2014	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.34
2015	0.01	0.04	0.06	0.17
2016	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.43
2017	0.01	0.03	0.05	0.06
2018	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.55
2019	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.52
2020	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.10
2021	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.20
2022	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.61
2023	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.24
2024	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.24
Average	0.02	0.06	0.05	0.25
S.D.	0.01	0.04	0.02	0.17
COV	55.47	74.54	37.56	68.69

Sources: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India

Conclusions

Quality of drinking water has been analyzed on the basis of human health. If the people of any area are suffering from water borne diseases, it can be said that the quality of drinking water is not good in India, The morbidity and death cases due to diarrhoea are highest but case fatality rate of cholera is highest among all water borne diseases in overall period since 2005 in India, the data clear shows that the people are still suffering from these diseases in India it means quality of drinking water in India on the basis of biological parameter is not good, even though we

are celebrating our 79th independence day and India is now emerging as a powerful economy in the world, but still the citizens of our country are not independent of unsafe drinking water. Quality of drinking water is not just an environmental imperative; it is a species-defying economic, societal, and political one. The dream of *Vikshit Bharat @2047* will be impossible without sustainable water management.

A combination of technology innovation, policy reform, industrial accountability, and community participation is the answer. Therefore, as India progresses, a focus on the

efficient use of water by establishing mechanisms to check pollution, promote rainwater harvesting and inter-sectorial cooperation in water management may alone ensure a water-secure future. All levels of government, industry, agriculture, and society as a whole must act now to protect water supplies for future generations.

Limitations

The paper is based on only secondary data. The paper will conclude the data of the drinking water and water borne diseases of the year of 2005 to 2024.

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